

Assessment of Human Resource Management Practices of a Community College

Chibert Largo Jala

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the human resource management practices of a community college as observed and assessed by the academic staff, support staff and administrators. It endeavors to present the human resource practices through its five (5) major components which include institutional goals, recruitment, selection, hiring, and placement, training and development, compensation, and performance evaluation.

The study employed the descriptive research design that deals with quantitative method using a survey questionnaire. The sampling design used is purposive which generated the total number of employees in the community college. The 115 respondents of the study were the 23 academic support staff which include the College Registrar, the librarian, the school's cashier and Disbursing Officers as well as the employees of the accounting office; 81 teaching personnel or teachers, and 11 academic department heads and administrators.

Findings of the study show generally highly practiced human resource management practices. Respondents strongly agreed on the various aspects of human resource management particularly on recruitment, selection, hiring, and placement of employees. Compensation of employees was also considered to be properly in place. However improvements can be made in employees' retirement plan and changes in the compensation package should be properly communicate to concerned employees. Also, there is a need to enhance the methods of recruiting job candidates and make the right advertising for recruiting employees.

KEYWORDS

Human Resource Management Practices, Compensation, Recruitment, Evaluation Performance

INTRODUCTION

Organizations today constantly wrestle with revolutionary trends like accelerating product and technological changes, global competition, deregulation, demographic changes; and at the same time, attempt to implement trends towards a service and information age society (Kane, 2000). In this midst of this business environment, one of the challenges facing many business organizations is the proper management of its human labor force. Society has now become knowledge-based where clearly human investment is considered the main supply and crucial to the survival of businesses. Organizations are competing increasingly for employees who have the best potential (Porter, 2001). Companies recognize that an important element in business management practices is the need to successfully motivate high talent employees who survive organizational restructuring, downsizing, consolidation, reorganizing or re-engineering initiatives (Clark, 2001).

For many organizations, strategic staffing has become an important issue because the ability to utilize highly talented employees can be crucial to future survival (Whitner, 2001). Human resources management is costly because of the resultant bidding up of market salaries for experienced personnel; the costs of recruiting and training of new talents; building relationships and team work (Nussler, 2000).

Effective management of human resources, as the talents with critical sets of skills, is acknowledged as vital for the achievement of business growth and the building of organizational competencies. Some organizations strive to be the 'employer of choice' by creating a positive environment and offering challenging assignments that foster continued personal growth. They try to be an organization that outperforms its competition in the attraction, development and retention of people with business-required aptitude, often through innovative and compelling human resource programs (Clark, 2001).

This concern is shared by a local college in Southern Philippines. As it strives to provide quality education, the college employs teachers with impressive academic credentials and teaching experience from both private and public higher education institutions. However, due to limited items for permanent teaching positions and political interventions

in management decision-making of the community college, there was a fast faculty turnover over the years. The most qualified teachers resigned to get permanent teaching positions from other schools or pursue other opportunities. The institution has to recruit new teachers to fill in the vacant positions and even those without teaching experience were hired.

Planning for human resources looks at the totality of the personnel complement of an organization mainly for the purpose of ensuring an efficient and effective performance. It should be designed to foresee any conceivable situation that may arise and therefore must include the tasks of recruitment and selection process reflecting the quality of its people (Mondy, 1996).

Human resources training and development are career-advancement procedures that help the employees become more effective in fulfilling organizational goals. This function cultivates the individuals in an organization to become competitive and be able to cope with the constantly changing environment. HRD is a continuing process that begins as soon as the individual joins the local government unit (Mondy, et al., 2000).

The supposition of corporation incentives (Clark, 2001) is that the financial capability of the organization, incentives (financial and non-financial) may be given either to all employees (regardless of position or performance) or to selected ones based on their contribution to the organization. The management may also decide to give awards or citations to outstanding employees provided they meet the pre-determined criteria.

This study therefore focuses on the human resource practices of a community college as observed and assessed by the academic staff, support staff and administrators. It endeavors to present the human resource practices through its five (5) major components which include institutional goals, recruitment, selection, hiring, and placement, training and development, compensation, and performance evaluation.

METHODS

The study utilizes descriptive research design with the general profile of the respondents as well as the established Human Resource Practices of the college as the variables. The study also utilized a purposive sampling where all the support staff, teaching personnel, and school administrators

of the college served as respondents of the study. The 115 respondents of the study were the 23 academic support staff which include the College Registrar, the librarian, the school's cashier and Disbursing Officers as well as the employees of the accounting office; 81 teaching personnel or teachers, and 11 administrators.

A researcher-made instrument was utilized in gathering needed information from the respondents of the study. Part I is on the respondents' profile which include the personal characteristics such as age, sex, remuneration, job position, nature of employment, length of service, educational attainment and trainings. Part II of the research instrument deals with the implementation of human resource management practices of the school. The instrument was validated and highly reliable using Cronbach alpha analysis with the result of 0.741.

RESULTS

Profile of the Support Staff, Teachers, and School Administrators

In the respondents' profile regarding age, 46.09% or fifty-three (53) belong to the age group 30 years old below. Forty six (40%) of the respondents belong to age group of 30-40 years old. Eight respondents (6.96%) belong to age group of 41-50 years old. Eight respondents (6.69%) belong to age group of 50 years old and above. Majority of the college personnel are young professional who belong to the age range of 30 years old below. These groups of individual are often characterized as young person with fewer personal responsibilities so they can take risks and work for a better start-up employment (Hallie Crawford, 2008). At this stage, an individual actually experiences the work culture in his first job. The learning institution has more female employees (65%) than males. Civil status shows that fifty seven out of 115 (49.57%) of the respondents are single and fifty five (47. 83%) of the respondents are married while three (2.61%) are separated.

The length of service in the academic institution shows that respondents with 2 to 5 years in the service registered the highest number with 64 (55. 65%). This is followed by those who are newly hired employees every semester with a total of 28 (24.35%). The least number belongs to

those who have been in the service between 10 to 13 years with only 11 or 9. 57%.

For professional advancement, data show that 34 (29.57%) of respondents have units in Masters Courses and 28 (24.35%) earned their Master's degree. Respondents with college degrees recorded 21 (18.26%) who are mostly from academic support staff. In the CHED memorandum order no. 2 and paradigm to R.A 7722 as "Higher education act of 1994" it explicitly states that higher learning institutions should employ teaching staff with master's degree units in order to teach in the tertiary level.

The respondents' remuneration showed 78 (67.83%) earned a monthly income above 20,000 pesos and 21 (18.26%) got 10,000 to 14,999 pesos while there are also 16 (13.91%) who are earning 15,000 to 19,999. The remuneration package like allowances and government benefits are enjoyed only by regular and casual employees. 18 of the respondents (15.65%) have enjoyed the remuneration package while 97 (84.35%) employees are excluded from these benefits.

Nature of Employment indicates that majority of the respondents are non-tenured or Job Order (J.O) occupying 97 (84.35%) among personnel, while there are only 16 (13.91%) who are regular and two (1.74%) are casual employees. Every end of the semester, population of Job Order employee fluctuate its number. The contracts of JOs who are hired to teach are renewed every semester, while the academic support staffs differs in one academic year. The 84.35% are not entitled to security of tenure and such privileges and perks enjoyed by regular or permanent employees, such as membership with the GSIS, sick leave, vacation leave, maternity or paternity leave, attendance in trainings and seminars, 13th month pay, year-end bonuses and cash gift.

Furthermore data also present that 34 (29.57%) of the respondents have attended at least 3 confirmed trainings followed by 27 (23.48%) who attended only 2 confirmed trainings. There are 9 (7.83%) of the respondents who have the highest number of trainings followed by 10 (8.70%) with 4 confirmed trainings attended. It signifies that career advancement depends on the human resource training and development and the organizational goals cultivate the individuals in an organization to become competitive and be able to cope with the constantly changing environment (Martirez, 2001).

Human Resource Management Practices

Table 1
**Mean Distribution on HRM Practices
 Considering Institutional Goals**

Item No.	INSTITUTIONAL GOALS	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION
1	a. The vision, mission, and goals of the college help achieve educational goals.	1.08	.27	Highly Practiced
2	b. Employees' orientation on the vision, mission and goals of the college is necessary.	1.10	.31	Highly Practiced
3	c. The vision, mission, and goals of the college are reflective of its main school activities.	1.06	.24	Highly Practiced
4	d. The HR Department is mandated to disseminate the vision, mission, and goals of the college to all employees.	1.07	.26	Highly Practiced
5	e. These vision, mission, and goals should be internalized by the employees of the College.	1.05	.22	Highly Practiced
Over-all Weighted Mean		1.07		Highly Practiced

Table 1 shows that employees rated all the 5 activities of the organizational goal as highly practiced. The highest weighted mean is on the statement "Employees' orientation on the vision, mission and goals of the college is necessary" (\bar{X} = 1.10). The employees saw the necessity of the orientation relating to the college vision, mission and goals (VMG) as it served them a guide in planning and implementing varied activities in line with their VMG. Although the orientation of VMG got the highest mean, its effect in the individual was rated lowest as reflected in the statement "these vision, mission, and goals should be internalized by the employees of (\bar{X} = 1.05). Internalization is an individual task and this can be facilitated during meetings where the employees can interact during meetings where the VMGO is used as basis for analysis in terms of planning, implementing and evaluating activities.

Table 2
**Mean Distribution on HRM Practices
 Considering Recruitment, Selection, Hiring, Placement**

Item No.	RECRUITMENT, SELECTION, HIRING, PLACEMENT	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION
1	A written policy statement, which identifies the principles of the work guides recruitment of new employees.	1.70	.65	Highly Practiced
2	A clear and defined recruitment process should be followed by the school organization.	1.40	.59	Highly Practiced
3	An HRMO has the sole responsibility for the recruitment and hiring processes.	1.23	.42	Highly Practiced
4	Accurate job descriptions should be made.	1.63	.64	Highly Practiced
5	A clear definition of minimum qualifications criteria for the job, including input from the hiring supervisor should be rendered clearly to the applicants.	1.44	.50	Highly Practiced
6	Geographical scope of the search of employees should be properly defined	1.50	.60	Highly Practiced
7	Methods of recruiting of job candidates should be made accurately by the HRMO.	1.91	.66	Moderately Practiced
8	Exact information for advertising and recruitment should be used.	1.98	.55	Moderately Practiced
9	A predetermined record-keeping system to document recruiting activities should be made.	1.62	.59	Highly Practiced
10	A periodic audit the recruitment process for legal compliance, as well as to determine whether it successfully meets internal customer needs should be made.	1.24	.43	Highly Practiced
Over-all Weighted Mean		1.57		Highly Practiced

Table 2 presents the employees' assessment of the human resource management practices relating to recruitment, selection, hiring and placement. As indicated the over-all weighted mean is 1.57 with the

description of moderately practiced. Even if the direction of the result is not distinguished as highly practiced program in the institution, the methods of recruiting a job done by HRMO ($\bar{x} = 1.91$) and with the exact information for advertising used ($\bar{x} = 1.98$) has the highest mean value.

The delivery of recruitment services in this sector is further complicated by the need to balance role-based skills, departmental or divisional needs, and agency-specific requirements. Local Government sector recruitment must be well versed in placement processes that require specific documentation for each applicant. Recruiters need to prepare documents such as formal application forms, selection criteria, statement of claims, and referee reports. This requires a commitment from the recruitment consultants as they meet, select, and prepare candidates, create and submit formal applications, and brief candidates for the interview and selection process Kreitner (2009). This also presupposes the function of Human resource management officers to acquire, reduce or increase employees depending on their performance to the level that correspond to the needs of the organization.

Table 3
**Mean Distribution on HRM Practices
 Considering Training and Career Development**

Item No.	TRAINING AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION
1	They should have a designated person responsible for staff training and development.	1.42	.50	Highly Practiced
2	There should be a separate category in the human resource budget for training and development.	1.15	.36	Highly Practiced
3	A periodic review of training needs to reflect changes and improvement in programs, the organization long-range plans of the school should be well-prepared by the HRMO.	1.25	.44	Highly Practiced
4	There should be a written statement of training goals and priorities of the school	1.12	.33	Highly Practiced

5	There should be a formal process for conducting employee evaluation of training programs.	1.11	.32	Highly Practiced
6	School Administrators should be accountable for following up with employees to track the impact of training on performance and to support employee achievement.	1.33	.47	Highly Practiced
7	There should be a uniform training for all employees.	1.10	.30	Highly Practiced
8	There should be a formal educational reimbursement program.	1.17	.38	Highly Practiced
9	A written guideline for supervisory discretion in approving participation in training is necessary.	1.16	.36	Highly Practiced
10	A mandatory training requirement for support staff and teaching personnel employees is necessary.	1.12	.33	Highly Practiced
Over-all Weighted Mean		1.19		Highly Practiced

Table 3 presents the HRM practices of training and career development in which the mechanisms for the actual performance of every employee must be in place; the overall mean is 1.19 showing highly practiced approach.

It is also observed that the respondents' mean outcome of 1.10 as the highest mean value is "Highly Practiced" in the training of employees for personal and professional improvement. 1.42 has the lowest mean value in the area of staffing of personnel responsible for training the staff for certain development. Training and career development give benefits to every employee as well as the organization by conducting seminars and trainings every end of the semester. It aligns employee training and development efforts with the organization's mission, goals, and objectives. Martirez (2001) confers that in attempting organizational improvement in the current or future performance of an employee, increasing skills or knowledge in the particular subject also increases perfection in the workplace.

The training and seminars of employees during the end of 2nd semester where there is a length of time to establish training programs as to

assist employees in achieving their personal and professional development goals. Hence, regular trainings and career development to the employees are systematic.

Table 4
**Mean Distribution on HRM Practices
 Considering Compensation**

Item No.	COMPENSATION	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION
1	There should be a specific compensation philosophy, whether based on merit, pay-for-performance, incentives, or cost-of-living increases	1.07	.26	Highly Practiced
2	A compensation philosophy should be clearly stated in writing.	1.29	.45	Highly Practiced
3	A written compensation plan should be made and communicated to employees.	1.06	.24	Highly Practiced
4	The people and positions involved in designing, approving, and administering your compensation plan.	1.04	.20	Highly Practiced
5	The current and accurate job descriptions help employees work effectively.	1.06	.24	Highly Practiced
6	A well-written job classification structure contributes employees' productivity.	1.11	.32	Highly Practiced
7	Job classification and compensation issues should be settled immediately by the school authorities.	1.03	.20	Highly Practiced
8	The compensation levels should be set objectively in relation to external market factors and the financial conditions.	1.04	.23	Highly Practiced
9	The compensation levels should be reviewed at regular intervals. (at least every two years.)	1.01	.18	Highly Practiced
	<i>the following should be included in the compensation package:</i>			
10	Wages/Salaries	1.08	.34	Highly Practiced

11	Paid/Unpaid leave	1.98	.55	Moderately Practiced
12	Insurance Coverage	1.11	.41	Highly Practiced
13	Retirement Plans	1.98	.55	Moderately Practiced
14	Flexible spending plans	1.11	.41	Highly Practiced
15	The conduct of an annual compliance review of all compensation policies and practices should be done by the school management.	1.09	.28	Highly Practiced
<i>A well-defined process for determining the following is very important in school organization</i>				
16	starting wages/salaries	1.09	.28	Highly Practiced
17	wages/salary increases	1.07	.26	Highly Practiced
18	use of paid leave	1.04	.20	Highly Practiced
19	use of unpaid leave	1.70	.65	Highly Practiced
20	Changes in compensation packages should be well-communicated to employees.	1.98	.55	Moderately Practiced
Over-all Weighted Mean		1.24		Highly Practiced

Table 4 indicates that the human resource practices considering compensation has a mean of 1.24 which is highly practiced. The paid/unpaid leaves and retirement plans practices are considered moderately practiced with 1.98 since these are only received by regular and casual employees. For Lawler (1996), in order to meet the priorities being laid down at the domestic end of the organization, it is necessary to meet the expected level in accordance with the benefits they have received which not only motivates employees but also enable them render the best services the organization can sustain for the good of everyone.

The majority of the respondents are well compensated in relation to the nature of employment and various benefits were determined and classified with those who are tenured and non-tenured employees. Employees' compensation was properly reviewed every 2 years with a mean of 1.01 resulting to highly practiced. Compensations are determined through professional achievements or field of specialization is categorized.

The majority of the respondents are well compensated in relation to the nature of employment and various benefits determined and classified from those who are tenured and non-tenured employees. The compensation was properly reviewed every 2 years with 1.01 resulted to its being highly practiced. Compensations are determined through professional achievements or field of specialization is categorized.

Table 5
**Mean Distribution on HRM Practices
 on Performance Evaluation**

Item No.	EVALUATION	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The designated HR staff, is responsible for the design and administration of the performance management process including:</i>				
1	The formal performance appraisal process	1.11	.35	Highly Practiced
2	The disciplinary process	1.40	.50	Highly Practiced
3	Periodic audits of how supervisors carry out both functions	1.10	.31	Highly Practiced
4	The performance management process should be developed using a comprehensive job analysis.	1.07	.26	Highly Practiced
5	There should be trained supervisors in positive performance management processes to help employees improve performance.	1.87	.47	Moderately Practiced
6	The formal performance appraisal should be done on at least once a year.	1.23	.42	Highly Practiced
7	The formal performance appraisals based on clear job descriptions, performance expectations and standards, and regular supervisory feedbacks help employees improve work performance.	1.12	.37	Highly Practiced
8	The employees should help design or input in the development of their performance standards and expectations.	1.08	.33	Highly Practiced

9	The performance appraisal process should be explained carefully to employees.	1.15	.36	Highly Practiced
10	Employees' performance appraisals results should be kept confidential by the HRMO.	1.29	.45	Highly Practiced
11	Salary or pay should be commensurate to performance.	1.93	.61	Moderately Practiced
12	The performance appraisal process should be regularly evaluated.	1.44	.57	Highly Practiced
Over-all Mean		1.31		Highly Practiced

Table 5 presents the area of performance evaluation with overall rating of 1.31 considered “Highly Practiced” calculated. Two of the programs were rated moderately practiced. These are in the area of Human Resource Management personnel with a mean of 1.87 which involves supervision of employee’s performance and salary or pay commensurate to performance with a mean of 1.93 which anchored performance evaluation on teaching personnel as incentive for salary pay.

The performance evaluation includes employee development in its job description and organizational achievement. This is the basis for the employees accomplishments both personal development and organizational goals (Flippo, 2001).

The academic institution mostly hires its teaching personnel who enter as probationary employees with Job Orders (JO) status. Whitner (2001) stated that a probationary employee is one who, for a given period of time, is being observed and evaluated to determine whether or not he is qualified for permanent employment. A probationary appointment affords the employer an opportunity to observe the skill, competence and attitude. While the employer observes the fitness, propriety and efficiency of a probationer to ascertain whether he is qualified for permanent employment, the probationer at the same time seeks to prove to the employer that he has the qualifications to meet the reasonable standards for permanent employment.

CONCLUSION

The human resource management practices of a community college have been the focus by this study. The teaching personnel, support staff and administrative staff foster unity among themselves and express their ideas, opinions, and feelings to the school management. The HRM practices were properly managed in the area of compensation with the increases of salary of teaching personnel, academic support staff, and administrative personnel so that the employees take home pay could provide the basic needs of their families.

The school management provided enough dissemination in the recruitment, selection, hiring and placement of personnel for the human resource needs of the college. The employees considered the Human Resource Management practices were administered effectively and promptly, responding to the needs of teaching personnel. This involved predetermination on the standard procedure and status of their works. The immediate feedback of the personnel on the need for improvements in the college provided better interpretation in the area of compensation so that teaching personnel received proper evaluation to their work.

The College can further improve its human resource management practices by looking into its recruitment and selection of employees, accurate job descriptions, methods of recruitment of job candidates, approved language for advertising and recruiting, predetermined records for recruitment activities, motivation of workers, benefits, contracts, provision of equal opportunities, and salary or pay commensurate to performance.

The government and public sector can generate significant number of temporary, casual, and non-permanent placements in a given year, hence there is dire need of ensure accuracy quality of candidates that provide basic understanding of the needs of the institution.

REFERENCES

- Burrach, M. et al. (1996). *Strategic Human Resource Management and Development*. London, Oxford Press.
- Clark, J. (2001). *Managing Human Resources in the Corporate Organization. Twenty-first Century: Principles, Methods, and Approaches*, University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor.
- Crawford, H. (2008). *Flying Solo: Career Transition Tips for Singles*. Paperback. Publisher: Authentically Speaking.
- Dunn, E. and STEPHEN, H. (2000), *Job Analysis: Effective Management Tool*. Washington D.C: Bureau of National Affairs.
- Flippo, E. (2001). *Personal Management*. McGraw-Hill Companies. New York City, United States.
- French, H. (1990). *Human and Organizational Development*. London Oxford Press.
- Gutherie, J. (2001). *The Corporate Responsibility of Developing Human Capital*. New Jersey. Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- Kreitner, R. (2009). *Human Resource Management Planning*. New Tech Park, Singapore
- Lawler, B. (1996). *HRD Competitive Advantage*. Penguin Books, and Deetz, S.A., & Stevenson, S. L. New York: Harper & Row Publishers.
- Mahoney, J. (1984). *Contributions to the Resource-based View of Strategic Management*. Blackwell Publishing, 9600 Garsington Road, Oxford. UK and 350 Main Street, Malden, MA 02148, USA.

- Martires, R. (1998). *Human Behavior in Organization* 3rd edition. National Book Store. Mandaluyong City.
- Martirez, C. (2001). *Principles of Human Resource Management and Development*. National Book Store. Manila, Philippines.
- Monday, T. (1996). *The Effective Management of Human Resources in the Organization*. Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster/John Knox Press.
- Monday, T. et al. (2000). *Human Resource Management*. London: Pearson Education, Limited.
- Nussler, J. (2000). *International Perspectives in Management of Human Capital*. Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster Press.
- Porter, R. (2001). *Human Resource Management and Corporate Responsibility of Human Capital*. New Jersey. Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- Santos, D. (2002). *Recruitment, Retention in Competitive environment*. Career Development International.
- Straus, A. et al. (1999). *Human Resource Development and Management*. University of California Press, Berkeley, CA.
- Whitner, E. (2001). Do High Commitment, Human Resource Practices affect Employee Commitment? A Cross-level Analysis using Hierarchical Linear Modeling. In *Journal of Management*, 27 (5) 515-64.